

The passepartout wayfares of Covid-19, Cytokine storm and Kounis syndrome

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Abstract

Covid-19, caused by SARS-CoV-2, along with its cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, hematologic, mucocutaneous, respiratory, neurological, renal and testicular manifestations and further complications constitutes one of the deadliest pandemics in modern history. A common pathogenetic mechanism of these complications seems to be the Covid-19-induced complex and excessive immune response of uncontrolled release of interleukins, chemokines, interferons, tumor necrosis factors and colony-stimulating factors, the so called cytokine storm syndrome. Severe anaphylactic reactions with profound hypotension or hypoxemia can be also associated with release of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Insights from research in allergy/anaphylaxis-associated Kounis syndrome and Covid-19 immunology, strongly suggest that the same key immune cells may be involved in Covid-19 induced cardiovascular complications, anaphylaxis and the anaphylaxis-associated Kounis syndrome. Similarities in patho-physiology, etiology, clinical cardiac manifestations and therapeutic approaches of the severe Covid-19 cardiac complications and anaphylaxis associated Kounis syndrome might be proved beneficial for future treatments based on the antigenic substrate of the latter.

1. Introduction

The latest threat to global health is the ongoing outbreak of the respiratory disease caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), named Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19), firstly recognized in December 2019 in the city of Wuhan in Hubei province, China [1]. Covid-19, caused by SARS-CoV-2, along with its cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, hematologic, mucocutaneous, respiratory, neurological, renal and testicular manifestations and further complications constitutes one of the deadliest pandemics in modern history. In modern overpopulated world of almost 8 billion people, characterized by dramatic changes in environmental conditions, in conjunction with rapid development of intercontinental transportation and inadequate global public health mechanisms, viral diseases with significant infectivity may turn into global health threats. The Covid-19 pandemic has been spread in more than 180 countries, including the whole of Europe and the United States. Therefore careful investigation for similarities in clinical manifestation and correlated multi-organ complications could provide a better understanding on its underlying patho-physiology and trigger mechanisms, elucidating potential prevention and therapeutic strategies.

2. Virology and origin

Coronaviruses are enveloped positive single-stranded RNA viruses ((+)ssRNA) with a genome of 27-32 kb. SARS-CoV-2 belongs to the beta-coronavirus genera, while evolutionary analyses have demonstrated bats and rodents as gene sources [2]. Regarding its origin, conspiracy theories for laboratory construction have been widely spread through social media, but genetic data are not suggestive of this scenario. The receptor-binding domain in the spike protein is the most variable part of the coronavirus genome. Genetic manipulations in laboratories have been performed on available viral reverse-genetic systems, allowing researchers to introduce scheduled mutations. However, genetic data clearly reveal that Covid-19 is not derived from any previously used virus backbone [3] supporting the evidence that

Covid-19 is a novel coronavirus, originated from natural selection either in an animal host pre or post zoonotic transfer [4].

Infection is initiated with virus attachment to its cellular receptor on the host cell surface. Covid-19 spike protein (S-protein) binds with the angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor on the epithelial cells' membrane. Covid-19, transmission via the respiratory system, could be facilitated by the abundant ACE2 expression by human respiratory epithelium [5]. Given that ACE2 is also expressed in vascular endothelium, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, brain, and renal tissue as well as testicular epithelium, these organs are rendered potential targets for infection [6].

Although the vast majority of patients infected with Covid-19 are asymptomatic or present mild symptoms, some patients may develop moderate or severe complications, such as acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), acute cardiac injury, coagulopathy with thromboses, renal and hepatic dysfunction, accompanied by increased risk of mortality [7]. A common pathogenetic mechanism for these complications seems to be Covid-19-induced proinflammatory state the so called cytokine storm syndrome [7].

3. The Cytokine storm

Cytokine storm is a complex and excessive immune response accompanied by excessive or uncontrolled release of pro-inflammatory cytokines that can be triggered by a variety of external stimuli such as severe viral infection as influenza [8], certain drugs [9] and cancer immunotherapeutic agents [10]. Cytokine storm has been described also as an unfortunate consequence and adverse effect of some monoclonal antibody medications as well as adoptive T-cell therapies [11-13]. In addition, severe anaphylactic reactions with profuse hypotension or hypoxemia can be also associated with release of pro-inflammatory cytokines [14].

The term "cytokine storm" was used, for the first time, in 1993 in a case of a graft-versus-host disease [15]. Its association with infectious diseases started in early 2000 in several reports related to lymphohistiocytosis [16], group A streptococcus [17], influenza virus [18], variola virus [19] infections, and severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) [20]. In

2005, it was applied in the context of avian H5N1 influenza virus infection [21]. In the H1N1 influenza pandemic the cytokine storm was also considered as the cause of death in several victims [22].

In cancer immunotherapy, autoimmune toxicity results from an antigen-specific attack on host tissues when the targeted tumor associated antigen is expressed as well on nonmalignant tissues [23].

Another condition, the so called cytokine release syndrome, is increasingly recognized, and it is caused by high-level immune activation, constituting a non-antigen specific toxicity. Such high immune activation is necessary to mediate clinical beneficial effects via modern immunotherapies [10].

In severe anaphylaxis with either hypotension or hypoxemia, a number of cytokines are released and elevated in blood serum during the acute phase, correlating with the presence of hypotension [24]. During the allergic respiratory reactions, mediators may be largely confined to the airways' tissue, without concomitant increase in blood serum levels. Alternatively, other mediators such as anaphylatoxins, may play a significant role during respiratory reactions [25].

The cytokine storm is considered to be one of the major causes of ARDS, usually associated with multiple-organ failure [26], playing an important role in the process of disease aggravation [27, 28].

In critically ill patients suffering from Covid-19 infection, the cytokine storm can result in further deterioration of their clinical condition therefore its effective detection and suppression is of paramount importance for a positive outcome.

4. The cytokine "network"

The cytokine storm, and the consecutive dangerous complications arise from the combined effects of several immune-active molecules (TABLE 1) [29-31].

TABLE 1. Cytokines constituting the cytokine storm

<p>1. Interleukins (ILs)</p> <p>IL-1 (IL-1β, IL-18, IL-33), IL-1α, IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, IL-8, IL-9, IL-10, IL-13</p> <p>2. Chemokines (CXC, CC, C, CX3C)</p> <p>CXCR3, CXCL8, CXCL9, CXCL10, CXCL11, CCL2 (monocyte chemoattractant protein), CCL11 (eotaxin)</p> <p>3. Interferons (IFNs):</p> <p>Type I IFNs (IFN-α, IFN-β) Type II IFN (IFN-γ) Type III IFNs IFN-λ1, λ2, λ3 (IL29) IL-28α IL-28β</p> <p>4. Tumor Necrosis Factors (TNFs)</p> <p>5. Colony-Stimulating Factors (CSFs)</p> <p>Granulocyte colony stimulating factor Macrophage colony stimulating factor</p>
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The different types of cytokines associated with the cytokine storm include:

1. Interleukins (ILs), so named because their fundamental function appears to be the communication between (inter-) various populations of white blood cells (leucocytes-leukin) and further regulation of the immune cell differentiation and activation. They are produced by almost all stromal cells ,mast cells, B-lymphocytes, T-lymphocytes, macrophages, monocytes, dendritic cells, and other non-lymphocytic cells, such as fibroblasts, endothelial cells, keratinocytes, glomerular mesangial cells and tumor cells [32]. They induce an increase of the acute phase signaling, activate epithelial cells, and mediate the transportation of immune cells to the infection site , also triggering the production of secondary cytokines [33]. Interleukins consist the largest group of cytokines.

2. Chemokines are small secreted proteins that can bind to one or more of 21 G-protein-coupled receptors. Chemokines serve as chemoattractants to recruit inflammatory cells from endothelium and epithelium into the inflammation site [34], especially those of the immune system, contributing to innate and adaptive immune function and development. The role of one specific chemokine, CXCL10 (previously referred to as interferon- γ inducible protein of 10 kDa, or IP-10), has been highlighted in ARDS and coronary syndromes [35]. Chemokines are emerging as the second largest family of cytokines.

3. Interferons (IFNs), so named because they interfere with virus replication and play the central role in establishing innate immunity to viruses and other microbial pathogens [36]

4. Tumor necrosis factors (TNFs) called by their ability to cause an hemorrhagic tumor necrosis post injection into experimental animals, are involved in the pathogenesis of septic shock. They are regarded, today, as the central cytokines in acute viral diseases, including those caused by influenza virus, dengue virus, and Ebola virus. They are released from immune cells in the acute phase of inflammation and infection. They have been correlated with a number of chronic inflammatory and autoimmune diseases [37].

5. Colony-stimulating factors (CSFs), so named because they support the growth and differentiation of various elements in the bone marrow. They are proteinic components of a cascade that induces cytokine production by macrophages at sites of inflammation, further perpetuating the inflammatory reaction [38]. They divide into different subtypes based on their action as : called granulocyte colony stimulating factor (G-CSF), macrophage colony stimulating factor (M-CSF), and granulocyte-macrophage colony stimulating factor (GM-CSF)

5. Cytokine storm clinical manifestations

The cytokine storm clinically manifests during activation and further release of inflammatory cytokines by large numbers of lymphocytes (B-lymphocytes, T-lymphocytes, and/or natural killer cells) and/or myeloid cells (macrophages, mast cells, monocytes, eosinophils, dendritic cells, or even endothelial cells

lining blood vessels) [9]. Pleiotropism characterizes each individual cytokine that can exert multiple functions depending upon the cell that produces it and the target cell(s) upon which it acts. The severity of cytokine storm and the symptom onset may vary according to the inducing cause and the magnitude of immune cell activation.

The clinical symptomatology of the cytokine storm includes a variety of symptoms and signs (TABLE 2) that range from mild, flu-like symptoms to severe life-threatening manifestations depending on the severity of inflammatory response.

Table 2. Clinical signs, symptoms and laboratory findings associated with cytokine storm

Constitutional: anorexia, arthralgias, fever, fatigue, headache, myalgias, malaise, rigors

Skin: Edema, rash, rigor

Gastrointestinal: Diarrhea, nausea, splenomegaly, vomiting

Respiratory: Hypoxemia, hypoxia, interstitial pulmonary edema, respiratory failure, tachypnea

Cardiovascular: Acute heart failure, arrhythmias, hypotension, increased cardiac output (early), potentially diminished cardiac output (late), myocarditis, stress cardiomyopathy, tachycardia, troponin elevation, QT prolongation, widened pulse pressure

Blood and coagulation: Bleeding, coagulopathy (increased Prothrombin Time (PT), reduced International Normalized Ratio (INR)), cytopenias, disseminated intravascular coagulation, elevated D-dimer, febrile neutropenia, hypofibrinogenemia

Renal: Acute kidney injury, azotemia, renal failure

Hepatic: Elevated liver enzymes, hepatomegaly, hyperbilirubinemia, liver failure

Neurologic: Altered gait, aphasia, confusion, delirium, difficulty in word finding, dysmetria, hallucinations, headache, mental status changes, paresis, seizures, tremor

Arthralgia, fatigue, fever, headache, muscular pains and rash constitute mild symptoms but in severe cases hypotension, hypoxemia and fever can further lead to severe and uncontrolled systemic inflammatory response accompanied by vasodepressor-circulatory shock, and vascular leakage, as in anaphylactic shock [39]. Furthermore, thrombotic vascular events, disseminated intravascular coagulation, and multi-organ system failure may be induced.

Respiratory complications are common in patients with cytokine storm. Mild cases may display cough and tachypnea but can also progress to ARDS with dyspnea, hypoxemia, and evidence of bilateral opacities on chest X-ray [9]. ARDS may sometimes require mechanical ventilation due to inability to protect the airway secondary to neurotoxicity rather than actual respiratory distress [40].

Neurologic symptoms and signs are also encountered during cytokine storm [41] and range from mild confusion, hallucinations, headaches, word-finding difficulty, to aphasia, cranial nerve palsies, hemiparesis, seizures and somnolence.

Cardiovascular complications of cytokine storm in general and in viral infections in particular may include arrhythmias, myocarditis, myocardial ischemia, pericarditis, and type 1 (atherosclerotic plaque rupture) and type 2 (secondary to an ischemic imbalance) myocardial infarction and heart failure [42].

6. Cytokine storm in Covid-19, Cytokine surge in anaphylaxis

The immediate-type of generalized hypersensitivity reaction that affects multiple organ systems and manifests, at its most severe form, by bronchospasm, upper airway obstruction, hypoxemia, hypotension, collapse and cardiovascular complications including Kounis syndrome [43] is anaphylaxis (ana-phylaxis means 'opposite protection' or 'against protection', whereas prophylaxis in Greek means 'protection').

Since the era of histamine, thought to be the principal mediator of anaphylaxis, a range of other mediators, similar to those of cytokine storm in

Covid-19 patients, have been implicated in human anaphylaxis, in vitro cell stimulation studies, and in animal models [44]. The anaphylaxis-implicated mediators resembling cytokine storm molecules are released from mast cell and other inflammatory cells and include, apart from histamine, mast cell tryptase, chymase, and cathepsin-D, newly synthesized cytokines and chemokines such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), IL-1, IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, IL-8, IL-9, IL-13, lipid-derived mediators, platelet activating factor, prostaglandin D2, leukotriene LTB4, cysteinyl leukotrienes LTC4, LTD4, and LTE4, complement breakdown products such as the anaphylatoxins C3a, C4a, and C5a, products of contact system activation including bradykinin, and a variety of inflammatory and anti-inflammatory products of eosinophil activation [45]. Indeed, mast cells and other inflammatory cells participate in an inflammatory vicious cycle (see figure below), in which each can activate the other via multidirectional signals and be co-activated like a "ball of thread".

For example, mast cells can activate macrophages [46] and may enhance T-cell activation [47]. Inducible macrophage protein 1a may activate mast cells [48], while CD169-macrophages activate CD8 T cells [49]. T cells may

mediate mast-cell activation and proliferation [50] and regulate macrophage activity [51]. Monocyte chemoattractant protein 3 is a most effective basophil- and eosinophil-activating chemokine [52]. Dendritic cells may initiate autoimmune responses and stimulate T cells with resultant macrophage activation [53]. Interactions between lymphocytes, monocytes, macrophages, and mast cells increase vascular permeability, similar as in anaphylaxis-associated Kounis syndrome [54], via release of TNF, IL-1 β , IL-6, CXCL8 (IL-8), macrophage migration inhibitory factor, CCL2 (also known as monocyte chemoattractant protein-1, MCP-1), high mobility group box-1 and matrix metalloproteinases [55]. The latter can promote plaque disruption or rupture leading to myocardial infarction via activation of their zymogen forms interstitial collagenase, gelatinase, and stromelysin [56].

Surprisingly, the same clinical manifestations as in Covid-19, namely fever, headache, bone pain, skin rash, life-threatening hemorrhagic fever, shock syndrome with major features of high levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines, vascular leakage, thrombocytopenia, hemorrhage, hypotensive shock, myocarditis and myocardial infarction are encountered in other viral diseases including dengue fever—a mosquito-transmitted viral infection [57].

7. Kounis syndrome, Mast cells and Viral infections

Anaphylactic, allergic, hypersensitivity, or anaphylactoid reactions associated with cardiovascular disorders were initially characterized as acute carditis, morphologic cardiac reactions, or rheumatic carditis of unknown pathophysiology and were attributed to serum pathology. The allergic angina syndrome, as a coronary spasm representing a manifestation of endothelial dysfunction or microvascular angina leading to allergic acute myocardial infarction, was described some 30 years ago [58] and in 2005 was named by American researchers as the Kounis syndrome [59].

The pathophysiology of this syndrome includes inflammatory mediators released during an anaphylactic event from mast cell activation and degranulation in the context of other interacting cells, including T-lymphocytes, macrophages, eosinophils, monocytes, eosinophils and dendritic cells TABLE 3 [60].

TABLE 3. Mast cell : the “pleiotropic cell” and its inflammatory mediators participating in "Cytokine storm" able to induce the Kounis syndrome	
Preformed mediators	Newly synthesized mediators
Biogenic amines	Cytokines
Histamine , renin, angiotensin II, serotonin	Interleukins 1,2,3,4,5,6,9,10,13,16
	Interferon- γ
Chemokines	Macrophage activating factor
IL-8, MCP-1, MCP-3, MCP-4, RANTES (CCL5)	Tumor necrosis factor - α
Enzymes	Growth factors
Arylsulfatases, carboxypeptidase A, chymase, kininogenases, phospholipases, tryptase, cathepsin G	Granulocyte monocyte colony stimulating factor Fibroblast growth factor Nerve growth factor, stem cell factor , VEGF
Peptides	Arachidonic acid products
Bradykinin, corticotropin releasing hormone, endorphins, endothelin, somatostatin, substance B, vasoactive intestinal peptide, urocortin, vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)	Leukotrienes Platelet activating factor Prostaglandins Thromboxane
Proteoglycans	
Chondroitin, heparin, hyaluronic acid	

Although mast cells consist numerically a minority in this inflammatory cascade, they influence decisively the inflammatory process. Platelets also participate in this cascade via activation of their corresponding receptors by thromboxane, histamine, and platelet activating factor. Moreover, platelets also express high affinity IgE fragment crystallizable (Fc ϵ RI) and low affinity IgE Fc ϵ RII/CD32 receptors that constitute potential targets for many antigens [61]. Potential trigger factors of the Kounis syndrome include drugs, metals, foods, environmental exposures, and clinical conditions. Viral infections seem to play an important role in the cascade of mast cell activation. There is evidence that mast cells participate in host responses to certain viruses, but their precise roles in such settings remains to be elucidated [62]. Indeed, human and rodent mast cells express toll-like receptors (TLR3s), a class of proteins expressed on sentinel cells such as macrophages and dendritic cells,

that can recognize structurally conserved molecules derived from microbes [63]. These molecules play a key role in the innate immune system. These receptors can be activated by viral double-stranded RNA to release various chemokines and cytokines, including IFN- α and IFN- β [64]. Viral activation of mast cell associated-cytokine production might also insult the airway tissue and the coronary arteries, culminating in ARDS and in immunology associated Kounis syndrome [65].

It has been proposed that co-stimulation of human and rodent mast cell populations in vitro with Fc ϵ RI and certain TLRs can induce mast cell release of various pro-inflammatory mediators, suggesting another mechanism through which bacterial or viral infections might exacerbate atopic asthma and other IgE- and mast cell-associated disorders such as Kounis syndrome in vivo [61].

Moreover, mast cells can be infected by some viruses as dengue virus and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) [66, 67]. There is evidence that human mast cells can represent reservoir of persistent viral infection. Further mast cell exposure to TLR2, -4, or -9 ligands can trigger virus replication in latently infected cells. IgE-Fc ϵ RI interactions may in turn influence virus co-receptor expression by mast cells, thus establishing their susceptibility to infection with CXCR4-tropic and R5X4-tropic variants [68].

Dengue virus has been associated with immunological mechanisms such as antibody-dependent enhancement [69]. Indeed, opsonization of dengue particles can bound in immune complexes with non-neutralizing antibodies, leading to increase in infection rate in crystallizable fragment receptor-bearing cells, such as mast cells, dendritic cells and monocytes and higher levels of viral replication.

In subjects infected with HIV, IgE antibodies directed against HIV-1 gp120 and Tat proteins were demonstrated to be increased [70]. These molecules can induce human mast cell migration, functional activation in vitro, and further release of IL-4 and IL-13 from human mast cells and basophils. Moreover, Tat protein also can upregulate the β -chemokine receptor CCR3, expressed on lung mast cells that also constitutes a co-receptor of HIV-1 infection [71].

Therefore, the labyrinth of viruses, cytokines, mast cells, platelets and other interacting inflammatory cells with the released mediators acting on their receptors constitute the substrate for myocardial injury, coagulopathy, thrombosis, coronary complications and in particular the immunity associated Kounis syndrome, induced by mast cell activation.

8. Covid-19 and Myocardial infarction

According to recent reports ST segment-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), may represent the first clinical manifestation of Covid-19 [72, 73] . Therefore, further elucidation of the myocardial injury pathophysiology in patients with COVID-19 seems of paramount importance.

The Kounis syndrome induced by the release of inflammatory mediators through mast cell degranulation, may manifest as coronary spasm due to endothelial dysfunction or microvascular angina in patients with normal or nearly normal coronary arteries constituting subtype MINOCA (myocardial infarction with non obstructive coronary arteries), coronary thrombosis of type 1 myocardial infarction and stent thrombosis [74].

Similarly, the myocardial injury in patients with Covid-19 has been attributed to coronary spasm, direct endothelial or vascular injury, plaque rupture and microthrombi, hypoxic injury or cytokine storm [75]. Recently, a series of patients suffering from Covid-19 revealed a higher than expected incidence of stent thrombosis [76, 77], fact that was attributed to the underlying hypercoagulable state. Although thrombus aspiration was performed only in one patient, further histopathological study that may be valuable for identification of stent thrombosis cause has not taken place. Moreover, none of the other patients was evaluated for IgEs, specific IgEs and other inflammatory mediators that could have confirmed the presence of any type of cytokine surge and Kounis syndrome [61]. Although stent thrombosis is a multifactorial complication, the implanted “antigenic complex” of nickel alloys, polymers, eluted drugs, in conjunction with concomitant oral antiplatelet drugs and environmental exposures can induce Kounis syndrome. Thus far, all clinical reports, pathologic findings in all patients and animal experimental studies point toward inflammation with thrombus infiltration of various

interrelated and interacting inflammatory cells, including eosinophils [78], macrophages, T cells, and mast cells [79].

The histamine-2 receptor antagonist, famotidine, that stabilizes mast cells, has significantly reduced the risk for death or intubation (adjusted hazard ratio (aHR) 0.42, 95% CI 0.21-0.85) and also the risk for death alone (aHR 0.30, 95% CI 0.11-0.80) in hospitalized patients with Covid-19 [80]. Indeed, famotidine pretreatment can prevent endothelial cell permeability [80] attributed to histamine H₂ activation. It must be emphasized that famotidine and other antihistamines are drugs of choice for prevention and treatment of Kounis syndrome, as well as for prevention of myocardial ischemia/reperfusion injury induced by histamine H₂ receptor activation and further for peripheral vessel leakage prevention that is incriminated for the shock in anaphylaxis [81].

The value of corticosteroids is widely debated, but they have been widely used in syndromes closely related to Covid-19, including SARS, MERS, severe influenza, and community acquired pneumonia. Corticosteroids are also the drugs of choice for the treatment of Kounis syndrome. According to the RECOVERY trial, dexamethasone reduced the 28-day mortality in hospitalized patients with Covid-19 receiving invasive mechanical ventilation or oxygen at randomization to 29.3% as compared with 41.4% in the usual care group, but not among patients not receiving respiratory support [82].

Therefore, these similarities in pathophysiology, etiology, clinical cardiac manifestations and therapeutic approaches of the severe Covid-19 cardiac complications and anaphylaxis associated Kounis syndrome might be proved beneficial for future treatments based on the antigenic substrate of the latter. The use, for example, of humanized monoclonal antibodies to clear free IgEs and down regulate FcεRI expression might represent a new era for the treatment or prevention of such events. This has been already demonstrated for Kounis syndrome via anti-immunoglobulin E administration [83, 84].

9. Treatments and future perspectives

There are no Food and Drug Administration (FDA)-approved drugs for the treatment of Covid-19. FDA has created a special emergency program for possible therapies, the Coronavirus Treatment Acceleration Program, in an attempt to evaluate whether new treatments might be helpful and their further application to patient management as quickly as possible.

Main representatives of agents with antiviral activity include remdesivir, chloroquine-hydroxychloroquine, favipiravir, interferons, ivermectin, lopinavir/ritonavir and ribavirin.

Immunomodulatory regimens consist of azithromycin, IL-1 antagonist (anakinra), IL-6 antagonist (tocilizumab), janus kinase-2 inhibitors, colchicine, specific and non-specific intravenous immune globulins, convalescent plasma, humanized monoclonal antibodies and corticosteroids. These medications seem to exert a positive impact especially in severe cases with laboratory evidence of host hyperinflammatory response and or development of the macrophage-activation syndrome.

In the previous years, multiple viral and bacterial pathogens have been associated with atherosclerosis and experimental studies demonstrated an acceleration of atherogenesis following infection in animal models. Recent studies have reported that Covid-19 infection enhances activation of the immune system similar to the macrophage-activation syndrome that may further unmask any potential subclinical cardiovascular disease [85], promoting intra-plaque inflammation and subsequent pro-thrombotic activation. Based on these pathophysiological mechanisms, it appears possible that asymptomatic subjects infected with Covid-19 are predisposed to an increased risk of conversion from asymptomatic, subclinical, atherosclerotic disease into an unstable state with vulnerable plaques prone to thrombosis [86].

Virus activated mast cells release early inflammatory chemical compounds including histamine and proteases; while late activation may provoke the activation of pro-inflammatory IL-1 family members including IL-1, IL-6 and IL-33. It has been proposed that inflammation by coronavirus may be inhibited by anti-inflammatory cytokines belonging to the IL-1 family members [87].

The role of Vitamin D has been shown to be protective and safe against acute respiratory infections and dedicated studies about vitamin D levels in Covid-19 have been proposed [88].

Covid-19 has been associated with ST segment elevation myocardial infarction [73] but the course of the disease after their hospital discharge has not been clarified. Indeed, respiratory infections caused by influenza, parainfluenza, rhinovirus, respiratory syncytial virus, adenovirus, or human metapneumovirus have been found as independent predictors of hospital re-admission for myocardial infarction [89, 90], while influenza epidemics are associated with higher risk of out-of-hospital cardiac arrest [91].

Since pathophysiology and virulence mechanisms of coronavirus, and especially of Covid-19 is correlated with the function of their non-structural and structural proteins [92], similar effect could be expected in patients with Covid-19 infection. Implementation, therefore, of public health interventions may reduce the risk of out-of-hospital cardiac arrest during the current Covid-19 pandemic.

It seems that current literature on the treatment of Covid-19 is replete with anecdotal reports of therapeutic successes, small clinical trials, observational cohort studies, hypotheses, ideas and suggestions that claim efficacy and suspected success paying little attention to the effect of unrecognized confounders [93].

Indeed, several diverse medications with antiviral or immunomodulatory activity have been used in clinical practice, several others have been proposed but large clinical trials are needed to prove their efficacy.

Physicians should always keep in mind that "empty vessels make the most noise" as English author William Baldwin said and Aristotle's (384-322 B.C.)

dictum: “Not many is the good, but in the good, the many” (Ouk en tō Pollo to af, but en to af to poly=OYK EN TΩ ΠΟΛΛΩ ΤΟ ΕΥ ΑΛΛΑ EN ΤΩ ΕΥ ΤΟ ΠΟΛΥ).

10. Conclusion

Insights from research in allergy/anaphylaxis-associated Kounis syndrome and Covid-19 immunology strongly suggest that the same key immune cells are involved in Covid-19 induction, anaphylaxis and the anaphylaxis-associated Kounis syndrome.

It seems that an individualized treatment approach, tailored to each patient is required in Covid-19 cases; as severity of the disease, comorbidities, age, clinicolaboratory characteristics, indications for hyperinflammatory response, cardiovascular and myocardial complications and host factors are important determinants for disease progression.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors have no financial or other interest in the product or distributor of the product. Furthermore, they have no other kinds of associations, such as consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interests or patent-licensing arrangements.

Author Contribution

Each author contributed substantially to the work with access to all materials and data. NGK and SA wrote the initial draft. IK and VA provided systematic literature review. NGK and LS reviewed the final version of the paper. The corresponding author had final responsibility for the decision to submit for publication.

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